

Registration for BMF CP118: Environmental Values Consideration, Information Quality, and Solar Energy Adoption in the United States

Dear AISDL Team,

By registering to participate in the project entitled "BMF CP118: Environmental Values Consideration, Information Quality, and Solar Energy Adoption in the United States" on the SM3D Portal, I hereby declare that I have carefully read the working paper "Developing Bayesian probabilistic reasoning capacity in HSS disciplines" [1] and the foundational methodological book "The Mindsponge and BMF Analytics for Innovative Thinking in Social Sciences and Humanities" [2]. I fully understand, endorse, and commit to upholding the philosophy, principles, and ethical standards of the SM3D research community.

I commit to maintaining self-discipline in fulfilling assigned tasks within agreed timelines, upholding logical consistency and theoretical grounding in research work, and adhering to a culture of openness and transparency regarding data, code, and analytical procedures. I remain open to methodological innovations when they demonstrably improve the quality and robustness of the study.

I will treat all project members with respect and collegiality, and within my capacity, contribute to the long-term development of the SM3D community through knowledge sharing and ethical awareness.

Copenhagen, January 13, 2026

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References

- [1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH (2025) Developing Bayesian probabilistic reasoning capacity in HSS disciplines: Qualitative evaluation on bayesvl and BMF analytics for ECRs. <https://dipot.ulb.ac.be/dspace/bitstream/2013/397326/3/wp25008.pdf>
- [2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP (2022) *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.2478/9788367405119>